

ORIGINAL RESEARCH**Analysis of Rainfall Variability in the Province of Quirino**Mar Heisen A. Yanos^{1*}

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Abstract

The temporal variability of rainfall in Quirino Province was analyzed through the use of rainfall data of seven (7) rain gauges within the neighboring provinces like Nueva Vizcaya and Aurora. The length of record analyzed from 1997 to 2016. In this study, rainfall frequency analysis and consistency of rainfall data from the different stations through the use of double mass curve analysis was performed and analyzed. The annual series was used to screen each station's annual rainfall data while the province's average Thiessen rainfall was screened using maximum period series process. It was found out that all the data of the seven (7) rainfall stations were consistent. To attain allowable error in estimation of 10%, 5% and 1% for the mean annual rainfall the number of rain gauge station needed in the province should be 18, 72 and 1799, respectively.

Keywords: Double Mass Curve, Frequency Analysis, Rainfall, Rain Gauge, Temporal Variability, Thiessen

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1. Introduction

The Philippines has 7, 107 islands, lies on the western rim of the tropical Pacific just off the southeastern portion of the Asian continent, and is surrounded by the South China Sea and the Pacific Ocean. The high sea surface temperature rings a warm and wet climate to the Philippines (Flores and Balagot, 1969). Rainfall is the most important climatic element in the Philippines because agriculture, influenced by the annual and seasonal variation of rainfall, plays an important role in the Philippines economy (Jose, 2001; Akasaka, et. Al., 2007).

In the Province of Quirino some portions of the province lie on the East fall under Climatic Type III, which is characterized by no pronounced seasons. Rain is evenly distributed throughout the year. Dry season is from March to the early part of October while remaining days of October

to February are wet. The western portion falls under climatic Type IV which is characterized by rainfall or more or less evenly distributed throughout the year with dry season from March to August and wet from September to January (DENR-02). Rainfall variations are likely the most evident effects of the changes occurring on the earth's climate system (Ayugi et. al. 2016). An understanding to the temporal characteristics of precipitation is hence central to water resources planning and management, especially given the evidence of climate change and variability in recent years (Liu et. Al 2015). Such information is important in agricultural planning, flood frequency analysis, flood hazard mapping, hydrological modeling and water resources assessments (Gallego et. Al. 2011). Therefore, many studies on the temporal characteristics of rainfall in different part of the world have been conducted. As a result, this study